

Access to healthy and affordable food in rural areas – the role of online groceries and branded convenience stores

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Food stores are vital for access to healthy, affordable food, yet rural households face greater challenges than their urban counterparts in accessing food stores. Online groceries could help improve access among rural households, though coverage is uneven. Convenience stores (c-stores) play a key role in rural food accessibility, and their urban expansion has enabled growth of quick-commerce (small orders delivered rapidly), utilising c-stores as micro-fulfilment hubs. This abstract introduces ongoing research assessing whether rural c-stores could act as rural fulfilment hubs, enabling expansion of online grocery coverage in these areas, reducing urban-rural inequalities in food access.

KEYWORDS: Online groceries, q-commerce, rural coverage, food insecurity, The Co-operative Group (Co-op)

1. Introduction

The recently published ‘UK Food Security Report’ (DEFRA, 2024) recognises the important role of food stores in maintaining access to quality, affordable and healthy foods. It recognises that households most vulnerable to being food insecure include those in rural areas, where lower provision of food stores, dispersed populations and limited public transport may hinder access to food. DEFRA (2024) analysis found that households living in neighbourhoods classified as ‘rural villages, hamlets and isolated dwellings’ travelled an additional 265 miles per year, on average, to access food stores compared to households in ‘urban conurbations’. In addition to a time and financial cost associated with these longer journeys, there is evidence that rural households may also pay higher prices for groceries (Revoredo-Giha and Russo, 2020).

Online groceries (ordering groceries online for home delivery) could improve access to groceries in some of these neighbourhoods. Anderson et al. (2003) presented two competing theories regarding uptake of e-commerce. The efficiency theory suggests that propensity to shop online will be higher where physical accessibility is poorest, with uptake of online services acting as a tool to improve accessibility. By contrast, the innovation-diffusion theory suggests that e-commerce is primarily associated with urban centres of innovation, before diffusing to other areas. With reference to the grocery sector, academic studies have found evidence of both theories playing out concurrently (see Hood et al., 2020 for a summary), with recent (DEFRA, 2024) analysis highlighting that online groceries share of food expenditure was highest in rural areas (14.4%) compared to urban and suburban neighbourhoods (10.3% and 11.6% respectively).

This abstract sets the context for ongoing work evaluating the role of online groceries in providing access to healthy and affordable food in rural areas. It focuses on the potential for branded convenience stores – and specifically those operated by The Co-operative Group (Co-op) – to act as fulfilment hubs for online groceries, affording new opportunities to extend some online groceries services into underserved rural areas. Section 2 outlines the importance of physical stores for online groceries order fulfilment, presenting evidence of the resultant social and spatial inequalities in online groceries coverage. Section 3 highlights the potential of convenience stores as rural fulfilment hubs. Section 4

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concludes by outlining the analysis that will be completed and reported and GISRUK 2025.

2. Physical stores matter for online groceries order fulfilment, resulting in geographical inequalities in coverage

Unlike other online products that can be delivered via the postal service, there is no universal delivery coverage for online groceries. Orders are typically assembled at a local store from which delivery is made to the consumer using a dedicated fleet of delivery vehicles. Some retailers use Online Fulfilment Centres (OFCs) or ‘dark stores’ to boost store-based capacity in certain localities, or as a substitute for store-based fulfilment. In facing the ‘last mile’ costs associated with these orders, retailers determine the coverage (spatial extent over which they are willing to deliver), capacity (number of orders that can be handled) alongside the cost and availability of delivery slots.

A major web-scraping exercise that I carried out with colleagues in 2019 (reported in Newing et al., 2021) uncovered geographical inequalities in coverage of online groceries at the neighbourhood level across Great Britain (GB). We identified considerable neighbourhood-level variations in the number and range of online grocers that were available to households. Web scraping utilised one postcode per neighbourhood (LSOA or Data Zone) in England, Wales and Scotland (n = 41,729), interrogating retailers’ websites, using ‘check if we deliver to your area’ or similar tools. We focused on 8 key retailers offering online delivery of a trolley full of groceries, akin to a traditional ‘weekly shop’. Our analysis did not include app-based providers, typically offering speedy delivery of a small basket of goods. Whilst coverage in deprived neighbourhoods was generally good, coverage was comparatively poorer within rural areas, especially in the most remote neighbourhoods. We noted that remote rural areas suffered a dual-disadvantage of poor access to grocery stores, coupled with limited or no coverage of online groceries.

Expanding online groceries coverage into underserved areas is tricky given the predominance of store-based fulfilment. Working with data from a major supermarket, Urquhart et al. (2022) highlighted that the geographic gaps in supermarket provision in many rural areas means that there are a lack of potential fulfilment sites to provide coverage in these areas. To address this, there are some examples of retailers facing extreme last mile costs in order to meet rural demand. Morrisons offers daily deliveries to an online groceries collection point on the Isle of Skye, Inner Hebrides, Scotland. This collection point is over 100 miles by road from the nearest fulfilment store, inevitably resulting in high last mile costs in fulfilling deliveries to this online groceries collection point.

3. Convenience stores as micro-fulfilment hubs

In a 2023 article for *The Conversation* (Newing, 2023), I suggested that micro-fulfilment hubs could offer the solution, citing the example of Turkish grocer GETIR. Their UK expansion utilised a network of very small OFCs located close to demand (primarily in suburban neighbourhoods) that were used to fulfil small orders, delivered rapidly. Whilst their approach failed (GETIR exited the UK market in 2024), a number of grocers have now entered the quick commerce (‘q-commerce’) market via collaboration with online food ordering and delivery platforms ‘Just Eat’, ‘Deliveroo’ and ‘Uber Eats’.

2024 saw many grocers, including Morrisons, M&S, Waitrose and Tesco, announce ambitious expansion plans for their smaller-format convenience store (c-store) estates (Houlton, 2024b). This expansion of c-store portfolios is in part driven by their role as q-commerce fulfilment hubs. Like the OFCs used by GETIR, convenience stores are typically located in proximity to consumer demand in densely populated town and city centres and within suburban areas. This enables q-commerce orders to be fulfilled quickly and with reduced last mile costs, minimising the delivery distance between fulfilment location and consumer.

The Co-op, a major operator of c-stores, reports that it has 23% of the groceries q-commerce market in the UK, with ambitious plans for further growth (Houlton, 2024a). Co-op attribute the success and profitability of their q-commerce offering to their ability to utilise their large and dispersed

neighbourhood-level store estate. They have become the largest grocery provider on Deliveroo, Just Eat and Uber Eats (Houlton, 2024a). Unlike many other grocers, the Co-op convenience store estate extends well beyond urban centres into many rural areas, stretching the length and breadth of Britain, including stores in major urban conurbations and those serving outlying Scottish islands. Co-op report that this enables them to ‘cover 80% of the country’ with their q-commerce service (Houlton, 2024a). Whilst there is a lack of clarity around the metric Co-op used to ascertain coverage of their q-commerce service, it is clear that the Co-op store estate affords the potential for coverage which extends well beyond urban centres.

4. Convenience stores offer scope for rural expansion of online groceries

The Association of Convenience Stores (ACS, 2024) report that around a third of convenience stores are in rural areas. They also note the important role that rural convenience stores typically play within the communities that they serve, suggesting that they act as ‘mini high streets’ in their own right, offering a number of in-store services. They could additionally play a key role in extending online groceries coverage in these traditionally underserved rural areas. The important role of urban convenience stores in enabling growth of online groceries (via the q-commerce channel) is well established.

Focussing primarily on the Co-op store estate, the analysis that will be presented at GISRUK considers the extent to which convenience stores could boost access to online groceries in remote and rural areas, recognising the ‘efficiency theory’ (Anderson et al., 2003) and reducing the risk of food insecurity in these neighbourhoods. Analysis will draw upon commercial ‘retail points’ data to identify the geographic spread of convenience stores by area type. Changes in convenience store provision over time are briefly considered, prior to an examination of the changing Co-op store estate in rural areas. Analysis draws on the recently updated Rural Urban Classification (ONS, 2025), the official statistical classification distinguishing urban and rural areas, coupled with drive time data between residential neighbourhoods and the convenience store supply side.

The potential online groceries coverage that rural convenience stores could offer is considered, evaluating their contribution to food store accessibility. Findings will be framed in the context of major retailer c-store expansion plans, Co-op ambitions for its q-commerce growth and neighbourhood level food insecurity, recognising the important role that these stores could play in reducing urban-rural disparities.

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Biographies

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